

IMPACT OF GUJARATI INTERNATIONAL MIGRATION, DIASPORA IN DEVELOPMENT PROCESS OF GUJARAT STATE: AN EXPLORATORY ANALYSIS

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Abstract

According to the Ministry of External Affairs of India (2001), about 33 million people of Indian origin live outside the country. The population has increased substantially in recent times in the era of globalization, ICTs, and rapid modes of transportation. Gujaratis are a well-known social diasporic group of India. They have emigrated abroad to work as traders, people in business, shopkeepers, hoteliers, professionals, etc. Most emigrated after India became an independent nation to the USA, U.K., Canada, European countries, and so on as semi-skilled and skilled migrants. They have made a significant contribution to host countries and their origin areas. The impact of remittances, association groups, and philanthropic contributions in different ways by the emigrants or social groups at the micro and macro levels could be easily seen. The International migration or Diaspora from a region is likely to contribute significantly through the economic and social remittances to the development process over a period to the economies and communities at the place of origin. Social remittances are ideas, know-how, norms, values, knowledge, behavior, practices, and skills that migrants bring home or send home from abroad (Levitt, 1998, 2001; Levitt and Lamba-Nieves, 2011). There are more than 8 lakh NRI accounts in Gujarat, and the total deposits amounted to well over US\$ 40 billion (2006). The remittance flow from NRGs is so substantial that Madhapur, a Gujarat village, is amongst Asia's wealthiest. As noted earlier, Gujaratis are indulging more in social remittances in the forms of charity, gifts, and relief during disasters. The paper examines the understanding of the historical and contemporary pattern of international migration/ Diaspora from the state of Gujarat and its impact on the various levels of the development process of Gujarat based on the secondary and primary levels of data analysis by using the mixed methodology.

Introduction

Historically, diaspora has been associated with the Jewish people's dispersion from their homeland. However, the term's history in the scholarly literature has followed a pattern that is

no longer limited to forced dispersal. It has also accommodated alternative migrant experiences that fulfill the basic principles of diasporic circumstances. A diaspora exists primarily because it remembers its 'homeland'. The diaspora does not simply settle in other parts of the world; they establish their version of their homeland, including socio-cultural, economic, and political practices (Reeves and Rai, 2006). Indian emigration has occurred for ages, but it was only during the nineteenth and twentieth centuries that massive movements to other areas of the world happened. With a population of approximately 33 million, individuals of Indian descent live in almost all the countries of the world and they constitute more than 40% of the population in many countries outside India like Fiji, Mauritius, Trinidad & Tobago, Guyana, and Surinam. Broad patterns of Indian migration may be divided into three categories: (I) emigration to British, French, and Dutch colonies beginning in the 1830s; (ii) emigration to industrialized nations following World War II; and (iii) recent movement to West Asia (Bhat, 2003).

Concepts & Theoretical Background:

The term "Diaspora" has long been used to describe the Greeks throughout the Hellenic world and Jews following the destruction of Jerusalem in the early sixth century BCE. Diasporas are defined by their dispersal from a common origin. This might be a shared history and collective identity based on a shared socio-cultural experience rather than a specific geographic origin. However, most Diasporas have maintained ties with their homelands and among the scattered populations themselves.

In the 1980s, as argued by Safran, the term "diaspora" was used to denote several groups of people, including expatriates, expellees, political refugees, immigrants, and ethnic and racial minorities. Furthermore, as he pointed out, the phrase now indicated a wide range of distinct peoples who either applied for the title or had it bestowed upon them. Given their size, historical experiences, collective narratives, and varying links to homelands and host lands, they were destined to be a more diverse set of diasporas than the groups defined in the earlier phase (Cohen, 2008).

It was further stated that in the postmodern world, identities have become DE territorialized, built, and deconstructed in a fluid and dynamic manner; as a result, conceptions of diaspora have had to be drastically reordered in response to this complexity. Similar terms, such as transnationalism, hybridity, cosmopolitanism, and creolization, all address complicated flows, variety, and multi-locality in different ways (Cohen, 2008). Transnational perspectives on migration became prominent in the 1990s as scholars explored not just the experiences of the migrants in a new state but also their relationships to their homelands, real or imaginary. Glick

Schiller (1999) described transnational migration as a movement pattern in which people maintain social links within the polity from which they originated, even after crossing borders and settling in a new state (Kadekar, 2009).

Transnational is defined as 'reaching beyond or transcending national boundaries'. It has gained momentum as there are growing linkages between the non-state actors, mainly people, as well as ideas and goods across national borders (Rai and Reeves, 2009). Today's world migration has resulted in transnational diasporic communities that are linked by culture, ethnicity, language, and religion and with which they engage. The advancements in information and communication technologies have brought diasporic groups closer together, and the mobility of people entails the exchange of money, skills, technology, ideas, lifestyles, and commodities. Appadurai (1993) refers to this as technoscapes, mediascapes, technoscapes, ideascapes, and so on (Kadekar, 2009).

Indian Migration & Diaspora: Geographical Distribution and Its Impact

According to the latest UN data published in the World Migration Report 2022, India had the most citizens residing abroad of any country in the world in 2020 as depicted in the chart below. As of mid-year, little fewer than 17.9 million people born in the nation were residing abroad. Mexico and Russia, both huge nations with large populations, finished second and third, with 11.2 million and 10.8 million people living abroad, respectively.

Figure 1: Top countries of origin for international migrants in 2020 and 2023.

Source: (<https://www.statista.com/chart/30803/top-countries-of-origin-for-international-migrants/>)

The nineteenth and twentieth centuries saw an enormous exodus of indentured laborers, traders, professionals, and British government officials to British, French, Dutch, and Portuguese colonies in Asia, Africa, Latin America, and the Caribbean. Labor migration to Mauritius, Uganda, Nigeria, Guyana, Hong Kong, Fiji, Canada, Japan, Jamaica, Thailand, and other destinations began in the 1830s. This indenture system was later abolished in 1917 as a result of an anti-indenture ship movement organized by Indian nationalists (Jain, 1993; Clarke et al., 1990).

In the post-World War II period, a second wave of emigration occurred, primarily to industrialized nations in North America, Europe, Oceania, and West Asia. The first batch of Indians migrated during the British Raj. However, a significant migration occurred only after India's independence. The vast majority of these Indian migrants worked as professionals. People of Indian origin from Africa and the Caribbean also migrated to England during this period. Because of their relative wealth, Indian migrants across the industrialized world have been able to retain substantial contacts with India. Another factor is the flow of remittances and investments (Bhat, 2003).

Gujarati International Migration & Diaspora: Development Perspectives

One of the often-studied links between the diaspora and the homeland is that of finance or remittances, which is essential in the development and betterment of the family and homeland. Other forms of linkages and exchanges also help in the development of people and homelands like the exchange of social and cultural ideas. This exchange of ideas and remittances has led to progress in the home states due to the progressive ideas brought by their diasporas from abroad. Another form of development is the introduction of newer technologies by the diaspora that help in the improvement and development of their homeland. This can be seen in the contribution to the building of schools, hospitals, and universities by the diaspora and in their commitment to Philanthropic work in their homelands. It is also visible in the religious exchanges among the Gujarati diaspora across the various countries and commitment to its continuation, for example, The Swaminarayan or BAPS Temple has members across the world in the Gujarati community, especially the Patel community, who maintain contact and exchanges with each other and the homeland.

It is estimated that the number of Gujaratis living outside comprises about 1.5 million, out of which half a million reside in the USA (Sahoo 2006). According to sources in NRG Centre, Ahmadabad, about 6 million Gujaratis are living abroad spread over 120 countries. On the other hand, based on NSS 64th Round, the estimated number of emigrants from Gujarat in

2007-08 was only 0.18 7 million. There is not only a need to validate the estimate but also to understand the emigration process.

Interest in the global involvement of migrants and diaspora organizations has grown rapidly in recent years. A wide range of international entities are currently investigating the connections between migration and development in homeland. One of the most important ways diasporas contribute to economic progress is by spreading skills, technology, and information across borders. Diasporas, in this respect, are a major source of dissemination back to their home nations.

The literature emphasizes the importance of diasporas in economic growth. Both Bahar (2020) and Brinkerhoff (2008) investigate the potential for diasporas to contribute to the development of their home countries, with Bahar emphasizing economic gains and opportunities and Brinkerhoff discussing the various ways in which diasporas can contribute, such as remittances, investment, and knowledge transfer. Mohan (2002) and MacGregor (2008) present concrete instances of this potential, with Mohan emphasizing the problems and opportunities connected with displacement and MacGregor emphasizing the positive influence of skilled migrants on Somaliland's growth. These studies highlight the important role that diasporas may play in the growth of their home nations.

It is well known that the strategies of India's freedom struggle originated from among the Indian emigrant communities, many of them were Gujaratis, under the leadership of Mahatma Gandhi, who landed in South Africa in 1893 as a young barrister at the age of 24 on the invitation of Dada Abdulla –a Gujarati merchant. Gandhi Ji was the first Indian barrister, the first highly educated Indian to have come to South Africa and he returned to India in January 1915 (Chandra et al., 1989:170-175). Our national leaders with their roots in Gujarat had migrated temporarily to pursue higher studies in the UK during the British rule in India. The names that easily come to our mind are those of the Father of our Nation, Mahatma Gandhi; the Iron Man of India, Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel; Sardar Patel's brother Veer Vitthalbhai Patel; and the Civil Servant-turned-Politician-turned-Educationist, Dr H M Patel – all of whom are revered figures not only in the Gujarati but also the Indian psyche.

Gujaratis have been well-known for being skilled navigators and traders. The state's closeness to the Arabian Sea and the numerous ports that have been built along its coast have fuelled its economic and maritime interests. Individuals from diverse backgrounds started abandoning their traditional caste occupations and leaving their hometowns across the state (Ballard, 1978). Migration both inside and outside of India has also been influenced by climatic hardships, such

as the recurrent droughts in districts like Kachchh and other areas of the Saurashtra region (Shah, 2002).

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Safran and Cohen both try to describe the characteristics of a diaspora, where one of the most important characteristics of the diaspora is their continued relationship with their homeland, whether real or imaginary, and dedication towards its betterment (Cohen, 2008) and these characteristics are evident in the Gujarati diaspora.

Social & Economic remittances

Remittances play an essential role in the interplay between migration and economic development. Remittances are defined as the fraction of international migrant workers' earnings remitted home that plays an important role in the economics of sending nations (Russell, 1986). Michele Tuccio and Jackline Wahba (2020) reviewed economic literature on social remittances as economic, social, and political attitudes and norms that are conveyed through migration. Financial remittances, on the other hand, are in the form of cash or products sent by migrants to their home countries. Migration is a complicated process involving not just the exchange of money but also ideas, practices, and social capital (Tuccio, 2020). These "social remittances" can impact political landscapes, as evidenced by immigrants' influence on social movements and campaigns (Lacroix, 2016). The contrast between individual and collective remittances

and their capacity to influence regional and national transformation broadens the idea of these social remittances (Levitt, 2011). However, how these remittances are received varies, with financial remittances being more readily accepted than non-material ones, such as democratic principles, Western work culture, and so on (Gershoni, 2013).

D. Ratha, Sanket Mohapatra, and Elina Scheja (2011) conducted a literature assessment on the development impact of migration and remittances on origin and destination countries, specifically in the South. Their work summarises early arguments on migration's effects on climate change, democratic principles, demography, national identity, and security. There is an attempt to make a few policy recommendations, including better-integrating migration into development policies in both the South and the North, improving data collection on migration and remittance flows, leveraging remittances to improve recipient households' and countries' access to finance, improving recruitment mechanisms, and so on. It is often believed that the welfare repercussions of migration on the origin nation are primarily favourable, such as increased income from remittances, access to funding, and tapping into the knowledge and resources supplied by the international community of the migrant diaspora are the key ways migration alleviates poverty. However, not all consequences are positive: migrant exploitation by fraudulent recruiters or employers is allegedly frequent; separation from family may be difficult for some migrants; and large-scale immigration can pose severe challenges to a nation's sovereignty (Ratha, 2011).

Research on remittances in Gujarat shows that these financial transfers play a substantial role in the state's economy. Jones (2014) and Bhagat (2017) emphasize the importance of remittances in sustaining migrant workers' and their families' livelihoods. Tumbe (2011) discusses the increase in remittances in India and their influence on source region inequality in a larger framework. However, further study is needed to investigate the unique characteristics and procedures of remittances in Gujarat, as well as their potential for increasing financial inclusion.

Sidel (2003) reports that the Community Foundation Silicon Valley (CFSV) is believed to have contributed US \$10 million for relief activities in Gujarat in 2001 and 2002 after the killer earthquake; the American India Foundation (AIF) US \$2.2 million for Gujarat-related activities by mid-2002; and the Asian American Hotel Owners Association (AAHOA) US \$500,000 for relief activities in Gujarat after the killer earthquake of January 2001 and \$45,001 for setting up of a new school and undertaking other activities in Gujarat.

Gujaratis make up more than 60% of all Indians in North America. Gujarat accounts for 16% of all investments in India. Gujarat's business hub, Ahmedabad, is the seventh-biggest city in India. The world's fastest-growing city is Surat. The greenest capital city in all of Asia is Gandhinagar.

One of Gujarat's most prolific business communities is the Patidar community of the Patels, which historically belonged to the Charotar area of Gujarat or the district of Anand. This area has a high percentage of families with emigrated family members. They were part of the emigration under British rule and later post-independence migrations (Rutten and Patel, 2007). This community is also closely related to the Swaminarayan sect of Hinduism. It is a highly influential religious Indian diaspora that contributes to developing their home districts and villages in Gujarat.

Due to the large presence of the Gujarati diaspora in many industrially developed countries and their status as an established business community, they have a strong role as a visible Indian diaspora community in the homeland and host land. They contribute in various ways to their families, villages/cities, and homelands, and their role in the development of Gujarat through economic and socio-cultural linkages is vital.

Observations from the Field

It has been observed that migration has taken place the most in Gujarat from the different Patel communities across the state. There are different groups of Patidar or Patel communities in Gujarat like the 27 gam or the 24 gam.

In Gandhinagar district, in the Urban areas the migration that has taken place is a mixed community and type of migration but a large concentration of immigrations have taken place from Kalol (both urban and Rural) and in villages like Nardipur that have large diaspora population. The migration has mostly taken place to the US by the Patel community from this area. There is also a lot of student migration to Canada and Australia.

The Gujarati Patel diaspora is deeply involved in the development of their villages by investing in infrastructural development, investments in businesses, health and education. The community members also help each other with finance and information sharing. An example is the new Nardipur village Panchayat, the funds for which were donated by their diaspora and the village park.

Figure 1 New Park and Lake inaugurated in Nardipur, Nardipur, Gandhinagar district, Gujarat.

Figure 2 Nardipur Village's new Panchayat built with donations by its diaspora, Nardipur, Gandhinagar district, Gujarat

In Kachchh, the Kachchhi Leva Patel community has the most diaspora. They mostly migrated to Africa to work for the British and then generally to the United Kingdom after political instability in the region after the late 1960s. One of the richest villages in Asia, Madhapar, is in Kachchh. The Kachchhi Leva Patel community has helped a lot in the development of their village. From the schools, hospitals and public amenities like parks and temples. They play an active role with philanthropic activities and regularly visit their homeland. In an Interview with the Principal of M.S.V High school in Madhapar, Sri M.B. Zala, he informed that the Gujarati diaspora regularly donates to the school for its renovations and sponsors education of deserving in-need students.

Figure 3PI Project Staff Team conducting Interview with Sri M.B. Zala, Principal of M.S.V High School, Madhapar, Kachchh, Gujarat

Conclusion: Gujarati diaspora has a strong community and religious identity and contributed extensively through transfer remittance and socio-cultural, spiritual, and social organizations across borders. Gujarati diaspora has been an active contributor to the development of its place of origin or home state. Gujarat is received its direct and indirect forms economic contribution through philanthropy, economic and social remittances for funding children education, healthcare, and community development initiatives, which help to create developmental activities the state's infrastructure which promote the overall impact the economy of state of Gujarat.

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References

- Cohen, R. (2008). *Global Diasporas: An Introduction* (2nd ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203928943>.
- Rai, R., & Reeves, P. (Eds.). (2008). *The South Asian diaspora: transnational networks and changing identities*. Routledge.
- Kadekar, L. N., Sahoo, A. K., Bhattacharya, G., & Bhat, C. (2009). *The Indian diaspora: historical and contemporary context: essays in honor of Professor Chandrashekhar Bhat*.
- Bhagat, R. B., Das, K. C., Prasad, R., & Roy, T. K. (2017). International out-migration from Gujarat, India: the magnitude, process, and consequences. *Migration and Development*, 6(3), 448-459.
- Safran, W. (1991). *Diasporas in modern societies: Myths of homeland and return*. *Diaspora: A journal of transnational studies*, 1(1), 83-99.
- Russell, S. S. (1986). *Remittances from international migration: A review in perspective*. *World Development*, 14(6), 677-696.
- Hiralal, K. (2013). "Daughters of Gujarat in the diaspora": immigrant women, identity and agency in Natal. *Journal for Contemporary History*, 38(1), 1-21.
- Lacroix, T., Levitt, P., & Vari-Lavoisier, I. (2016). *Social remittances and the changing transnational political landscape*. *Comparative migration studies*, 4(1), 1-5.
- Lacroix, T. (2018). *Unraveling the conceptual link between transnationalism and diaspora: The example of hometown networks*. In *Routledge Handbook of Diaspora Studies* (pp. 173-180). Routledge.
- Bauböck, R., & Faist, T. (2010). *Diaspora and transnationalism: Concepts, theories, and methods* (p. 360). Amsterdam University Press.
- Bokser-Liwerant, J. (2014). *19 Jewish Diaspora and Transnationalism: Awkward (Dance) Partners? In Reconsidering Israel-diaspora relations* (pp. 367-404). Brill.
- Vertovec, S., & Cohen, R. (1999). *Migration, diasporas, and transnationalism*. Cheltenham/Northampton, 315-316.
- Tuccio, M., & Wahba, J. (2020). *Social remittances* (pp. 1-13). Springer International Publishing.
- Gershoni, Y. (2013). *The Nature and Reception of African Migrants' Financial and Social Remittances*. In *ASA 2013 Annual Meeting Paper*.
- Levitt, P., & Lamba-Nieves, D. (2011). *Social remittances revisited*. *Journal of ethnic and migration studies*, 37(1), 1-22.
- Ratha, D., Mohapatra, S., & Scheja, E. (2011). *Impact of migration on economic and social development: A review of evidence and emerging issues*. *World Bank Policy Research Working Paper*, (5558).
- Britannica, *The Editors of Encyclopaedia*. "diaspora". *Encyclopaedia Britannica*, 7 October 2023, <https://www.britannica.com/topic/diaspora-social-science>. Accessed 10 November 2023.
- Kondapi, C. (1951). *Indians overseas, 1838-1949*. Madras: Oxford University Press.
- Clarke, C., Peach, C., & Vertovec, S. (Eds.). (1990). *South Asians overseas: migration and ethnicity*. Cambridge University Press.
- Jain, R. K. (1993). *Indian communities abroad: Themes and literature*. New Delhi: Manohar.
- Helweg, A. W. (1982). *Emigration from Gujarat: The effects*. *India International Centre Quarterly*, 9(1), 30-36.
- Schiller, N. G. (1999). *Transmigrants and nation-states: Something old and something new in the US immigrant experience*.
- Dr. Gautam, M.K. 2013. *Indian Diaspora: Ethnicity and Diasporic Identity*, CARIM-India RR 2013/29, Robert Schuman Centre for Advanced Studies, San Domenico di Fiesole (FI): European University Institute.
- Blanchy, S. 2008. *The Impact of Political, Economic and Juridical context on identifications in Indian Gujarati Diaspora: Examples from Western Indian Ocean Islands and France*.
- Dekkers, N., & Rutten, M. (2011). *Diaspora philanthropy from a homeland perspective: reciprocity and contestation over donations in Central Gujarat, India*. (ProGlo Working paper; No. 2). National Institute of Advanced Studies / Amsterdam Institute for Social Science Research. <http://www.nias.res.in/docs/urpp/ProGlo-WP2.pdf>.

- Dhak, B., & Shah, A. (2011). International migration from Gujarat: An exploratory analysis. Gujarat Institute of Development Research.*
- Vahed, G. (2013). An 'Imagined Community in diaspora: Gujaratis in South Africa. In Gujarat Beyond Gandhi (pp. 149-163). Routledge.*
- Sahoo, A. K. (2006). Issues of identity in the Indian diaspora: A transnational perspective. Perspectives on global development and technology, 5(1-2), 81-98.*